

The interaction between callus induction and plant regeneration media is shown in Table 2. Calli produced in G1 medium could be regenerated on either M3, M5, or M7 regeneration media. Calli produced in Fj should be regener-

ated on M4, M7, or SK-11; those produced in L8 should be regenerated on M2, M3, M4, M5, or SK-11. The highest percentages of green plants were produced on M4 and M7. ■

Hybrid rice yield trials in the Mekong Delta

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We compared seven IRRI-bred rice hybrids and two check varieties in 1990 wet (WS) and dry (DS) seasons. Twenty-day-old seedlings were transplanted at 20 × 15-cm spacing, in a randomized complete block design with three replications.

Yield performance of F₁ rice hybrids in Vietnam, 1990-91.

Cross	Duration (d)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Filled grains (no/panicle)	1000-grain wt (g)	Yield (t/ha)	Standard heterosis (%)
<i>1990 wet season^a</i>						
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	125	429 abc	118.6 a	28.0	7.6 a	+41.83
IR62429 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	116	396 abc	92.4 cde	26.6	6.7 b	+26.26
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	407 abcd	111.0 ab	28.8	6.0 bc	+16.40
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	106	473 a	97.3 bc	25.0	5.9 bcd	+13.89
IR62829 A/IR24 R	113	451 ab	80.0 bc	27.2	5.6 cd	+5.62
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	104	418 abc	96.0 bc	28.0	5.5 cd	+6.75
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	104	352 cd	87.6 e	30.4	5.4 cd	+4.42
MTL 58 (check)	120	369 bcd	89.0 cde	26.0	5.3 cd	
MTL 61 (check)	104	334 d	83.6 cde	22.6	5.2 d	
CV (%)		11.80	8.14			
<i>1990-91 dry season</i>						
IR62829 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	100	14	107.6	23.8	6.67	+17.02
IR62829 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	12	99.7	21.1	5.70	+5.60
IR58025 A/IR29723-143-3-2-1 R	107	13	113.1	24.9	5.40	
IR58025 A/IR9761-19-1 R	99	13	94.7	22.5	4.87	
IR62829 A/IR24 R	99	11	86.6	22.7	3.93	
V20 A/IR9761-19-1 R	87	11	85.2	24.7	3.40	
V20 A/Milyang 46 R	89	12	82.5	27.5	3.00	
OM576 (check)	101	13	103.4	24.0	5.40	
MTL 58 (check)	105	12	95.9	24.2	5.70	
cv (%)			10.0		5.4	
LSD (0.05)			14.5		0.40	
LSD (0.01)			14.5		0.53	

^aIn a column, yields followed by the same letter are not significantly different at the 5% level by DMRT.

Surveys of disease or insect incidence/severity in one environment are useful only if the information is related to other variables (e.g., climatic factors, crop intensification, cultivars, management practices, etc.). By itself, information on incidence in one environment does not increase scientific knowledge.

Yield potential

Performance of different height rice lines under intermediate deep water levels

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We evaluated 12 promising rice lines with different plant heights (semidwarf, semitall, and tall) and growth durations (90-180 d), and N level (0 and 40 kg N/ha) under intermediate deep water (up to 80 cm) during 1988. The experiment was laid out in a split-plot design with three replications, with rice cultivars in the main plot and N level in 15.8-m² subplots.

Experimental lines were direct seeded in dry soil 6 Jun, at 400 seeds/m² with 20-cm row spacing, and fertilized basally with 9 kg P and 17 kg K/ha. Germination was good.

Water in the field increased gradually from mid-Jun, to 76 cm on 10 Aug and 83 cm on 25 Sep. During most of the crop growth period, water level was 30-60 cm. Water receded gradually from early Oct. The crops matured in mid-Dec.

Application of N increased plant height and yield attributes significantly (see table). The four tall cultivars had significantly higher yields. They elongated faster as water level rose and flowered during the first week of Nov.

Grain yield decreased linearly with decreasing plant height, and the three semidwarfs had very low yields. Popular, short-duration upland cultivar Kalinga 3 virtually failed under deep water. Although this variety had panicle numbers similar to those of other varieties, its panicle size was considerably reduced, partly because of seed germination of matured panicles lying on the water surface and partly because of damage by birds after early maturity.

Local semitall cultivar Hathipanja had the highest 1000-grain weight but had

Growth and yield attributes of rice varieties under intermediate deepwater conditions (up to 80 cm). Cuttack, India, 1988.

Treatment	Cross	Flowering date (DAS) ^a	Plant height at maturity (cm)	Panicles (no./m ²)	Panicle weight (g)	Grains (no./panicle)	1000-gram weight (g)	Grain yield (kg/15.8 m ² plot)	Straw yield (kg/m ²)
Tall varieties									
CN573-2-21	Patnai 23/Jaladhi 2	2 Nov (161)	170	81	3.22	146	25.8	3.71	6.17
CN579-363-3-1	Jhingasail/Jaidhi 2	4 Nov (163)	160	90	2.99	139	25.8	3.48	5.50
ET10002	Jaladhi 2/Pankaj	2 Nov (161)	167	72	2.93	136	25.6	3.70	5.26
IET10006	Patnai 23/Pankaj	2 Nov (161)	176	68	3.26	149	25.5	3.49	5.25
Semitall varieties									
CR292-805I	Pankaj/Mahsuri	20 Oct (148)	129	91	2.65	130	21.2	2.81	4.34
CR687-2-10	Savitri/Jagannat//CR333	15 Nov (174)	137	68	2.37	151	20.1	2.15	3.50
CR1030	Waikoku/CR210-1014	25 Oct (153)	138	63	2.50	145	19.1	2.28	4.13
Hathipanja (check)		28 Oct (156)	143	65	2.81	99	30.1	2.48	3.92
Semidwarf varieties									
CR210-1016	Pankaj/Jagannath	28 Oct (156)	98	60	2.18	123	19.0	1.79	2.34
CR260-171	CR151-791/CR210-1014	2 Nov (161)	120	52	2.32	126	22.2	1.63	2.82
CR527-18-2	Agahania/Savitri	24 Oct (152)	121	64	2.47	101	26.1	1.72	2.92
Kalinga 3	AC540/Ratna	1 Aug (68)	113	71	0.89	37	18.9	1.01	1.16
SE	-	-	5	5	0.22	10	0.2	0.30	0.43
N fertilizer (kg/ha)									
0	-	-	135	62	2.52	115	23.2	2.20	3.47
40	-	-	142	76	2.74	131	23.4	2.83	4.41
SE	-	-	1	2	0.08	3	0.1	0.06	0.12

^aDAS =days after sowing.

fewer grains per panicle, for a yield similar to that of other semitall cultivars with relatively finer grain types. CR687-2-10, although it flowered very late (mid-Nov), produced a yield similar to that of semitall cultivars that flowered in mid-Oct.

Application of N hastened flowering by 4-6 d but increased stem borer incidence by 42%.

Grain yield had a significant positive correlation with plant height at maturity ($r = 0.904^{**}$), panicle weight ($r = 0.869^{**}$), and grains per panicle ($r = 0.665^{*}$). Panicles per m² (considered a major yield attribute of medium-duration dwarf varieties under shallow water and irrigated conditions) had no significant relationship with grain yield under excess water ($r = 0.572$ ns). Panicles per m² was low (less than 100/m²), which ultimately led to heavier panicles, and that influenced yield most.

These results indicate that tall, elongating cultivars with good panicle size that flower during the first week of Nov are better suited to intermediate deep water conditions. Panicle number appears to be the limiting factor for higher yields. □

Grain quality

Attaining higher volume expansion in popped rice

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Popped, puffed or expanded, and flaked rice products are prepared widely throughout major rice consumption areas in India. Appropriate varieties account for nearly 10% of the total rice produced. Parameters characteristic of the popping quality of rice include maximum proportion of popped grains, volume expansion (ml of popped fraction from 100 g rough rice), and separation of husk from the product.

The factors associated with popped rice quality may be variety, machinery,

and processing techniques. We studied the optimum conditions for several processing variables, using a grain roaster.

Volume expansion was maximum when grains with 14% moisture were roasted at 275 °C for 40 s with sand of 0.35-0.60 mm size, at a ratio of 1 rice:2 sand.

Using these standard conditions, we screened 28 varieties for popping quality. Six varieties with volume expansion 900-1,300 ml were considered good poppers. The remaining varieties with volume expansion 20-765 ml were poor poppers.

In samples of seven varieties harvested late, volume expansion ranged from 80 to 770 ml. This reduction appears to be due to the number of cracked grains in the late harvested samples (see table). Cracking-resistant and cracking-susceptible varieties

harvested at optimum moisture content (22-24%) did not show significant differences in popping quality. Late harvesting at 16-17% moisture content, however, resulted in a greater reduction of volume expansion in crack-susceptible than in crack-resistant lines.

In four varieties, germinated or parboiled rough rice showed 50% reduction in volume expansion, probably due to loosened husk and other factors related to changes brought about during these processing operations. Samples of seven varieties stored for 12 mo under ambient conditions showed enormous improvement in volume expansion.

Popular varieties Intan (volume expansion 1,300) and FT 12, a selection from Vani (volume expansion 935), proved to be good poppers with maximum husk separation. They can be recommended for yield and improved